

ASSESSMENT OF THE OPERATION EFFICIENCY OF WATER SUPPLY TREATMENT FACILITIES AND PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING WATER QUALITY

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Abstract. *The article discusses the problems associated with the ineffective operation of water treatment facilities, which leads to insufficient quality of purified water. Monitoring of the functioning of existing systems was carried out, the main reasons for their low productivity were identified. As a solution, the introduction of an ion-exchange purification method is proposed, which provides a higher degree of pollutants removal. The advantages of the ion-exchange unit are described, including its ability to remove nitrogen compounds effectively.*

Keywords: *treatment facilities, nitrogen compounds, ion-exchange method, water quality, monitoring, purification technologies.*

In the context of rapid growth of industrial production and population increase, the issue of environmental protection is becoming especially relevant. Pollution of water bodies caused by wastewater discharge is one of the most serious environmental problems of our time. Ineffective operation of treatment facilities leads to hazardous substances entering natural water bodies, which can harm ecosystems and human health.

Nitrogen compounds in wastewater are a major environmental problem facing water bodies around the world. These substances, including ammonium, nitrates, and nitrites, often enter water systems as a result of agricultural activities, industrial wastewater discharges, and inadequate wastewater treatment in urban systems. Elevated concentrations of nitrogen compounds can lead to eutrophication, the excessive growth of algae that causes oxygen starvation and death of fish and other aquatic organisms. In addition, high levels of nitrates can contaminate drinking water supplies when they enter groundwater. This poses a health risk to humans, especially children, as high levels of nitrates can cause methemoglobinemia, a condition in which the blood loses its ability to carry oxygen.

Poor performance of treatment facilities results in nitrogen compounds entering water bodies, where they can cause various negative consequences. Wastewater treatment is a key process for protecting water bodies from pollution and ensuring the safety of ecosystems. The efficiency of treatment facilities directly affects the state of the environment and public health.

Innovative solutions for environmental protection and rational use of natural resources are becoming a necessity for ensuring sustainable development. Modern wastewater treatment technologies, new methods of monitoring and resource management open up prospects for improving the condition of water bodies and reducing the negative impact on nature [1,2].

In this article, we will analyze data on the operation of water treatment plants in the summer and autumn periods, using information on the quality of wastewater at the entrance and exit of treatment plants.

To assess the efficiency of the treatment facilities, data were collected on the quality of wastewater at the entrance and exit of three different water supply treatment facilities located in Tashkent region. The study included:

1. Data collection: Information was obtained from wastewater treatment plant reports that indicated the levels of pollutants (ammonium nitrogen, nitrite nitrogen, and nitrate nitrogen) entering and exiting the treatment plant.

2. Data analysis: For each station, the cleaning efficiency indicators were calculated using the formula: $E_{cl.} = \frac{C_{in} - C_{out}}{C_{in}} \times 100$

3. Comparative analysis: Comparison of the obtained results between different treatment facilities made it possible to identify the strengths and weaknesses in their operation.

Laboratory measurements of nitrogen compounds concentration were carried out using the photometric method.

The monitoring results are presented in the table.

Table 1. Information on the efficiency of treatment facilities in summer period

Treatment facilities	Wastewater discharge point	Main pollutants	Qualitative composition, mg/l		Cleaning efficiency %
			in	out	
Chirchik city branch of "Tashkent water supply". Treatment facility 1 pool	Chirchik River	(NH ₄) ⁺	40,8	24,2	40,69
		(NO ₂) ⁻	-	1,16	0
		(NO ₃) ⁻	0,8	2,7	0
Yangiyul city branch of "Tashkent water supply"	Salar channel	(NH ₄) ⁺	24,0	24,0	0
		(NO ₂) ⁻	-	0,008	0
		(NO ₃) ⁻	0,33	0,48	0
Chinaz district branch of "Tashkent water supply"	Salar channel	(NH ₄) ⁺	44,6	0,32	99,28
		(NO ₂) ⁻	0,0	0,175	0
		(NO ₃) ⁻	1,3	1,7	0

Table 2. Information on the efficiency of treatment facilities in autumn

Treatment facilities	Wastewater discharge point	Main pollutants	Qualitative composition, mg/l		Cleaning efficiency %
			in	out	
Chirchik city branch of "Tashkent water supply". Treatment facility 1 pool	Chirchik River	(NH ₄) ⁺	24,4	18,7	23,36
		(NO ₂) ⁻	0,1	0,99	0
		(NO ₃) ⁻	0,5	1,9	0
Yangiyul city branch of "Tashkent water supply".	Salar channel	(NH ₄) ⁺	17,7	17,7	0
		(NO ₂) ⁻	0,01	0,011	0
		(NO ₃) ⁻	0,5	0,73	0
	Salar channel	(NH ₄) ⁺	2,1	2,0	4,76

Chinaz district branch of "Tashkent water supply"	(NO ₂) ⁻	1,99	0,21	89,45
	(NO ₃) ⁻	2,1	3,4	0

The data in the table show that the treatment facilities are not coping with the task and the cleaning efficiency does not meet the established standards.

Data analysis showed significant differences in the efficiency of different treatment facilities. The most efficient was Chinaz district with an ammonium nitrogen purification rate of 99.28%. At the same time, the Yangiyul city branch demonstrated zero purification efficiency for ammonium nitrogen, which indicates the need to upgrade equipment or change purification technologies. These results highlight the importance of regular monitoring and analysis of treatment facilities to identify problems and develop strategies for their improvement.

This study examines the main reasons for the inefficiency of water treatment facilities and proposes innovative approaches to solving water pollution problem aimed at preserving ecosystems and rational use of natural resources [3,4].

Fig. 1. Treatment facilities. "Tashkent water supply", Chinaz district

The main reasons for poor-quality cleaning of municipal water supply systems identified by the authors in the study of sewage treatment plants are:

1. Incorrect design calculations based on outdated population data and system load.
 - Result: Treatment facilities are unable to cope with wastewater volumes, resulting in insufficient treatment.
2. The use of outdated methods, such as mechanical and biological purification, which do not provide sufficient removal of nitrogen compounds.
 - Result: High levels of ammonium and nitrates in purified water.
3. Lack of modern technologies for continuous monitoring of water quality.
 - Result: Inability to respond promptly to changes in the composition of wastewater and optimize treatment processes.
4. Incorrect balance of nutrients and conditions for microorganisms responsible for nitrification.
 - Result: Reduced efficiency of ammonium and nitrate removal.
5. Outdated cleaning process management systems.
 - Result: The human factor and management errors lead to a decrease in the quality of cleaning.

6. Insufficient funding and lack of plans to upgrade equipment.

- Result: Equipment wear and tear and reduced productivity.

To solve the water supply problem, small businesses may want to consider implementing their own water purification and treatment systems. This will not only allow efficient reuse of resources, but also significantly reduce the cost of water supply.

The creation of such systems requires initial investment, but in the long term this will result in savings, reduced dependence on external water suppliers and a positive impact on the environment. The use of modern purification technologies, such as ion exchange and membrane filters or biological installations, will ensure high quality water for industrial needs [4].

In addition, the transition to independent water supply will allow enterprises to respond more flexibly to changes in legislation and environmental protection requirements. Thus, the introduction of water purification systems will become not only an economically feasible solution, but also a contribution to sustainable business development.

Ion exchange plants are a modern solution for wastewater treatment, which is increasingly considered as an alternative to traditional treatment plants. These technologies provide a high degree of pollutant removal, especially nitrogen compounds, which makes them attractive for various industries. Ion exchange technologies allow a high degree of removal of specific ions, such as ammonium and nitrates, which can exceed 99%. This is due to the ability to selectively capture ions, which makes the process more efficient than traditional methods, such as biological treatment or coagulation.

The advantage of ion exchange units is their selectivity, with ion exchange resins being able to be tailored to remove specific pollutants, allowing more precise control over the purification process [5,6,7]. In this case, ion exchange units are compact, taking up less space than traditional treatment facilities, which is especially important in confined spaces, and are fast, with the ion exchange process being faster than many traditional methods, reducing wastewater treatment time. Traditional treatment facilities often take a long time to achieve the required level of purification. They may also be less effective at high concentrations of certain pollutants. In addition, such systems require significant maintenance and operation costs.

When comparing ion exchange plants and traditional wastewater treatment plants, several key aspects can be highlighted, such as removal efficiency, flexibility, and economic costs. In this regard, ion exchange technologies show higher efficiency in removing specific pollutants and can be adapted to changes in the composition of wastewater, while traditional methods may require significant modifications. Also, although the initial investment in ion exchange plants may be higher, their efficiency and lower operating costs can offset these costs in the long term.

Ion exchange plants are an effective alternative to traditional wastewater treatment plants. Their high degree of pollutant removal, compactness and operating speed make them attractive for many industries. In the context of increasing water quality requirements and the need to comply with environmental standards, the use of ion exchange technologies is becoming increasingly relevant.

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